

Hard Sphere Fluids

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Using Henderson's hard sphere fluid equation of state in equation $\alpha/\beta_c = \rho Z_0 k$, the values of hard sphere diameter σ of argon have been evaluated at several temperatures (84–90 K). The residual thermodynamic properties, namely, pressure (P^*), Helmholtz free energy (F^*), internal energy (U^*) and entropy (S^*) have been calculated for Henderson's hard sphere fluid and compared with those calculated by Wilhelm for Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid. The results agree with one another for values of $V_0/V \leq 0.6$. Beyond $V_0/V = 0.6$ the results begin to disagree increasingly in the higher liquid density range.

AN important breakthrough in the development of significant structure theory (SST) of liquids was the formulation of the hard sphere fluid equation of state by Henderson¹. The usefulness of SST was further enhanced when it was shown that the theory could provide a reduced equation of state². SST may also be employed for the evaluation of hard sphere diameter σ of molecular liquids like argon by substituting the known values of expansion coefficient (α), compressibility (β_c) and the number density (ρ) of liquids at several temperatures in the equation³,

$$\frac{\alpha}{\beta_c} = \rho Z_0 k \quad (1)$$

and solving for σ by iteration method. In equation (1), k is the Boltzmann constant and Z_0 is the compressibility factor for hard sphere fluid which in case of Henderson's fluid¹ is

$$\frac{PV}{NkT} = Z_0 = 1 - \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \ln \left\{ 0.00967 \left[8 - 11 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \right] \right\} + \frac{3}{2} \frac{11(V_0/V)^2}{8 - 11(V_0/V)} \quad (2)$$

the fluid having pressure P and volume V at T K and V_0 is the close packed volume, $V_0 = N\sigma^3/\sqrt{2}$, N being the Avogadro number and σ the hard sphere molecular diameter. The value of σ was evaluated for argon at its boiling point 87.29 K (3.367 Å) and agrees reasonably well with the literature value⁴ (3.405 Å). The values of σ were also evaluated at several temperatures between 84 and 90 K (Table 1) and was found to decrease with temperature as reported by the previous workers although the temperature coefficient is rather small in comparison to the earlier results for Percus–Yevick fluids.

In this context it is important to recall the suggestion⁵ to incorporate the temperature coefficient of hard sphere diameters in the theory of the

TABLE 1—EFFECTIVE HARD SPHERE DIAMETERS FOR ARGON

T K	Expansivity* $\alpha \times 10^3$ K ⁻¹	Compressibility* $\beta_c \times 10^4$ atm ⁻¹	Density* g cm ⁻³	σ (Å) Present work**
84	4.45	1.93	1.402	3.384
86	4.47	2.04	1.396	3.373
87	4.49	2.10	1.390	3.370
88	4.51	2.16	1.388	3.369
89	4.53	2.22	1.378	3.366
90	4.56	2.28	1.414	3.320

*Experimental values of expansivity α , compressibility β_c , and density are from S. J. YOSIM, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, 40, 3069. **Calculated using equations (1) and (2).

liquid state. This is all the more important as the hard sphere fluid of Henderson was seen to produce correct temperature dependence of expansion coefficient⁶ while the equation of Carnahan–Starling or Percus–Yevick shows otherwise.

Using the definition of residual functions^{5,7},

$$X^*(V, T) = \int_{\infty}^V \left[\left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial V} \right)_T - \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial V} \right)_T^{\text{Perfect}} \right] dV \quad (3)$$

where, X represents any thermodynamic property, such as pressure (P), Helmholtz free energy (F), internal energy (U), entropy (S) and heat capacity (C_V), in combination with the Henderson's hard sphere fluid equation of state (equation 2), we derived the following equations for the residual thermodynamic functions. The relevant equation for residual pressure (P^*) is

$$\frac{VP^*(V, T)}{RT} = -\frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \ln \left\{ 0.00967 \left[8 - 11 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \right] \right\} + \frac{3}{2} \frac{11(V_0/V)^2}{8 - 11(V_0/V)} \quad (4)$$

Using the thermodynamic relation, $F = -\int PdV$ in combination with equation (3), we get the equation

for residual Helmholtz free energy, $F^*(V,T)$,

$$\frac{F^*(V,T)}{RT} = -\frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \left\{ \ln 0.00967 + \ln \left[8 - 11 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (5)$$

In addition to equation (3) we have used the relation,

$$\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial V} \right)_T = T \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial T} \right)_V - P \quad (6)$$

which allows incorporation of the temperature coefficient of hard sphere diameter, $l = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{d\sigma}{dT} \right)$, in the equation for the residual internal energy (U^*) given by equation (7),

$$\frac{U^*(V,T)}{RT^2 l} = \frac{9}{2} \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \left[\ln 0.00967 + \ln \left\{ 8 - 11 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \right\} - \frac{11(V_0/V)}{8 - 11(V_0/V)} \right] \quad (7)$$

The residual functions are related by the usual thermodynamic relations,

$$TS^*(V,T) = U^*(V,T) - F^*(V,T) \quad (8)$$

so that one can readily obtain the equation for residual entropy $S^*(V,T)$,

$$\frac{S^*(V,T)}{R} = \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \left[\ln 0.00967 + \ln \left\{ 8 - 11 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \right\} \right] + \frac{9}{2} \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) T \cdot l \left[\ln 0.00967 + \ln \left\{ 8 - 11 \left(\frac{V_0}{V} \right) \right\} - \frac{11(V_0/V)}{8 - 11(V_0/V)} \right] \quad (9)$$

It may be noted that equation (9) for residual entropy also contains temperature coefficient of hard sphere diameter. Straightforward differentiation of equation (7) with temperature T would yield the equation for residual heat capacity $C_V^*(V,T)$ which should contain l as well as its temperature coefficient.

We have employed equation (5) for the evaluation of residual Helmholtz free energy (F^*) for a wide range of the values of V_0/V (0–0.72), the same range as used by Wilhelm⁵ for Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid. The results are compared graphically with those calculated by Wilhelm for Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid. It is evident from Fig. 1 that the results agree with one another in the liquid density range around $V_0/V \sim 0.6$ in respect of the residual free energy.

It is interesting to note that the temperature dependence of hard sphere diameter affects the residual internal energy and entropy. We have employed equation (7) for the evaluation of residual internal energy $U^*(V,T)/RT^2 l$ for various values of V_0/V between 0 and 0.72. In the plots of the calculated values of residual internal energy against

Fig. 1. Plots of residual Helmholtz free energy vs V_0/V based on: (—) Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid (Ref. 5), and (---) Henderson hard sphere fluid: present work.

Fig. 2. Plots of residual internal energy vs V_0/V based on: (—) Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid (Ref. 5), and (---) Henderson hard sphere fluid: present work.

V_0/V (Fig. 2), we noticed good agreement with Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid upto $V_0/V \sim 0.6$. In evaluating the residual entropy (S^*) for given V_0/V by means of equation (9), we have arbitrarily selected two values of $l = -0.03 \times 10^{-8}$ and $-0.05 \times 10^{-8} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The corresponding plots of $S^*(V,T)/R$ against V_0/V are shown in Figs. 3 and 4 along with those based on the work of Wilhelm⁵ for Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid. It will be seen that the Henderson and the Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluids with $l = -0.03 \times 10^{-8} \text{ K}^{-1}$ yield values of residual entropy (Fig. 3) which differ even in the very low density region and becomes larger as the liquid density range is reached. With $l = -0.05 \times 10^{-8} \text{ K}^{-1}$, however, the agreement improves (Fig. 4) the value of the

Fig. 3. Plots of residual entropy vs V_0/V based on: (—) Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid (Ref. 5), and (---) Henderson hard sphere fluid: present work.

Fig. 4. Plots of residual entropy vs V_0/V based on: (—) Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluid (Ref. 5), and (---) Henderson hard sphere fluid: present work.

residual entropy for the Henderson and the Carnahan–Starling hard sphere fluids do not differ significantly upto $V_0/V=0.6$ beyond which, however, considerable deviation from one another begins to appear.

Thus the Carnahan–Starling and Henderson hard sphere fluids generally yield values of the various residual functions in agreement with one another upto $V_0/V=0.6$. Beyond $V_0/V=0.6$, we notice disagreement between the results from the two theories which becomes increasingly prominent in the higher liquid density range.

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